

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL APPROACHES TO THE CONCEPT “HISTORICAL-CULTURAL HERITAGE”

Ilkhom Khoshimov

Phd student of Uzbekistan scientific research institute of pedagogical sciences named after Kari
Niyazi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7997088>

Abstract. *The article covers the essence of the concept of "historical-cultural heritage". Based on investigations on the topic by several scientists, author has passed an analysis of the features and tasks of historical-cultural heritage on the basis of the functional approach.*

Keywords: *Historical-cultural heritage, socio-cultural problems, functional approach, cultural system, social system, normative state, balance.*

Among the modern socio-cultural problems and their regional characteristics, the problem of preservation and actualization of historical and cultural heritage objects in our country occupies one of the central places.

Its tension is clearly manifested in the socio-economic conditions of new Uzbekistan. The concept of "historical-cultural heritage" is very important in the process of knowing the place and importance of the historical-cultural national heritage during the educational process in secondary schools.

First of all, introducing the term "historical-cultural heritage", we emphasize the leading role of organized human activity in changing the object, place and its space. These organizational factors allow us to consider the socio-economic, geographical and political interests of the state.

The term "historical-cultural heritage" is a derivative combination of the concepts "cultural and historical" and "heritage".

Historical and cultural heritage is an important component of understanding the specific value characteristics of the country within the framework of the development of the whole civilization, at the same time, the heritage represents its future resource potential. "Historical-cultural heritage" in the above sense is a part of the state's national wealth, a set of material goods belonging to the society. It is these benefits that should ultimately determine the country's development and impact on the world stage.

At the same time, the historical-cultural heritage is the spiritual and material values (objects, places) collected by the society, which are learned as a result of the education and socialization of the individual. Renewal and enrichment of the historical and cultural heritage is carried out through the exchange of ideas and experiences, the study of the values and traditions of other nations.

This approach to historical and cultural heritage becomes the basis of new scientific views. The role of historical and cultural heritage objects is becoming more and more important, because in modern conditions, culture becomes a full-fledged component of society, which determines the level of spirituality and on which the future of mankind depends.

The terms "cultural heritage" and "historical-cultural heritage" are recognized by most researchers as the most relevant and comprehensive concepts, because both reflect the historical process of accumulation and translation of the common values of culture and nature.

At the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, there were two directions of attitude towards cultural heritage. The first can be conditionally defined as "traditional". According to this approach, the attitude to traditions has a political and ideological character, helps to return the values of the past, destroys development trends.

The following trend can be considered the opposite, because it is aimed at choosing cultural values, actualizing the historical-cultural heritage from the position of inclusion in the modern socio-cultural space, and does not see contradictions in the use of this resource.

In scientific approaches, the term "historical-cultural heritage" is considered from different points of view, because this concept is complex and multidimensional, has a number of semantic features and is interpreted as follows: "cultural heritage is a collection of objects of culture and nature, the stages of development of society and nature and reflect as values to maintain and realize a conscious society".

Therefore, we consider the problem of defining and describing cultural heritage to be relevant to this day. The authors' opinions on this matter are different, and sometimes diametrically opposed.

The most popular approach to revealing the essence of the concept of "historical and cultural heritage" is the cultural approach. For example, L.A. Klimov believes that cultural heritage can be appropriated and alienated depending on the harmony of ideological priorities. Also, according to him, it depends on the ideas about the importance of certain cultural objects for contemporaries, which explains the priorities of preservation of cultural heritage objects in different historical periods.

Culture critic D.N. Zamyatin has a different point of view, that heritage has a sufficient share of conservatism, which is a cultural slowdown that prevents the healthy and competitive development of culture, which can lead to its "freezing". Also, cultural difficulties and cultural patterns can be implemented as a cultural sieve through which other cultures and civilizations must pass. He identifies the stabilizing function of heritage in relation to culture and does not deny the dynamics of heritage, the development of culture leads to the development of heritage, its image, which changes with culture, because it is an integral part of it.

One of the most comprehensive approaches to defining the concept of "historical-cultural heritage" is the functional approach, which considers the various functions of historical-cultural heritage based on the concepts of different authors.

According to the authors' understanding, the tasks of historical-cultural heritage can be as follows:

D.S. Focusing on the noosphere concept of cultural ecology, Likhachev defines the function of temporal stabilization, while the historical-cultural heritage functions as a form of transmission and consolidation of the accumulated experience of mankind.

According to Yu.A. Vedenin and Yu.L. Mazurov, the territorial geographical function is distinguished, and the historical-cultural heritage is manifested as a material and immaterial value system included in the territorial complex.

M. E. Kuleshova defines the information function, which is the information potential of the historical-cultural heritage.

Yu.V. Chernyavskaya historical-cultural heritage determines the ethno-cultural function that is part of the national culture.

Cornelius Holtroff emphasizes the social function, and the historical-cultural heritage simultaneously serves as the basis of social solidarity.

I.K. Kuchmaeva defines the compensatory and recreational function of the historical-cultural heritage.

According to P. Burde and A. Burden, historical-cultural heritage has the function of cultural capital, and historical-cultural heritage objects have economic value.

A.V. Lisitskiy identifies a synergistic function, in which the historical-cultural heritage acquires a systemic character, becomes a synergistic system.

From all of the above, it can be concluded that the term and phenomenon of "historical-cultural heritage" is a complex organized accumulation system. Based on the functional approach, the following features of the historical-cultural heritage were developed:

- social importance;
- information aspect;
- intangible direction;
- geographical direction;
- economic direction;
- synergetic conditionality, etc.

At the same time, the constant existence of the "cultural heritage" category in the dynamics helps to expand and add to the subject and semantic field of heritage.

From the point of view of the institutional approach, "historical and cultural heritage" is considered as a social institution that operates in society and forms the sphere of culture together with other social institutions.

The systematic approach allows us to consider the "historical-cultural heritage" as a whole and integral system, while the main method of analysis within this approach is the division into subsystems, separating individual elements from the whole, not from the parts. Subsystems or parts of historical-cultural heritage are not only immovable or movable monuments of history, culture and nature, but also elements such as folk culture, traditions, crafts, traditional forms of nature management, historical technologies, ethno-cultural environment, natural environment. At the same time, inheritance is considered as a system in which individual objects cannot be preserved with each other and outside of the environment.

From the perspective of the functional approach, each element of culture is functionally necessary to satisfy certain human needs. Elements of culture are considered in terms of their place in an integral cultural system. Cultural system is a characteristic of social system. The normative state of social systems is self-sufficiency, balance, harmonious unity. It is from the perspective of this normative situation that the functionality of cultural elements is evaluated.

The main tasks of historical-cultural heritage are as follows:

- socio-creative function, as a mechanism for identification of historical-cultural heritage, as a center for collecting and storing information on ways of providing life, as a participant in the formation of spatial and temporal coordinates of the world landscape;

- an anthropo-creative function consisting of the role of the historical-cultural heritage in the birth and development of a person, his cultural and methodological self-identification.

- the compensation-relaxation function, which is carried out when a person is immersed in another culture or the culture of the past. As a result of this situation, a person gets rid of stress.

This effect can be achieved by interacting with your favorite cultural expressions (visiting a gallery and viewing pictures, listening to your favorite music, etc.).

Within the framework of the approach of adaptive activity, culture is considered as a method of activity, as well as a system of extra-biological mechanisms that stimulate, program and implement adaptive and transformational activities of people. Two aspects of human activity interact: internal and external. In the process of internal activity, motives are formed, the meaning that people give to their actions, the goals of actions are chosen, schemes and projects are developed.

It is a type of culture that imbues internal activities with a certain value system, offering associated choices and preferences on a mentality level. Historical-cultural heritage plays an important role from the point of view of this approach, because it helps to fill the internal activity of people with a certain value system with the help of tangible and intangible heritage, and the external activity of people should be aimed at preserving and renewing historical-cultural heritage.

The use of synergetics as a theory of self-organization of complex systems in the field of social knowledge makes it possible to overcome dogmatism and one-dimensionality in the understanding of cultural heritage, to create a new model of heritage by identifying its true characteristics, and to expand the scope of knowledge of cultural heritage as self-awareness.

The articles and studies of representatives of the synergistic approach to the definition of "historical-cultural heritage" had a significant impact on the confirmation of the thesis concept.

Scientists like N. Moiseev, A.P. Nazaretyan, O.N. Astafieva and V.V. Melnik were the first who emphasize the human dimension of anthropo-social-cultural systems and actualize the involvement of the individual in the process of self-organization.

Considering the concept of "historical-cultural heritage" from the point of view of the economic approach, we pay attention to the theory of cultural capital. In this theory, heritage is defined as an economic value that represents public interest and includes aesthetic, historical, social, spiritual and educational values.

French researcher A. Burden elaborates on this idea and argues that developing cultural heritage and making it an "asset" contributes to economic and general cultural heritage. In his opinion, the more effective development of the cultural heritage of the population will be helped by its involvement in economic processes. Taking this into account, the reason for the development of a certain sector of the economy is the activity aimed at protecting the heritage. Such a sector of the economy can be considered cultural tourism, where cultural heritage is dominant, which attracts tourists with its characteristics and resources and helps to identify the individual.

The analysis makes it possible to formulate a definition of the actualization of cultural and historical heritage, through which we define the activities aimed at preserving and introducing objects of historical and cultural heritage into modern culture, the process of introducing it into economic and social circulation by capitalizing objects of cultural and historical heritage, as well as the preserving of historical and cultural heritage by adding it to the educational and social life of the secondary school, through capitalizing of the objects of cultural and historical heritage.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 19 dekabrda "Modiy turmush sharoitlarini muxofaza qilish ob'ektlari sohasidagi vaziyatni tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'riidagi qarori. www.lex.uz

2. “Alohida muhofaza yaratgan tarixiy-madaniy hududlar tuzish va ularni saqlash tartibini tartibga solish nizom”. www.lex.uz
3. Vazirlar Mahkamasining «Nomoddiy yashash ob'ektlarini muxofaza qilish, asrash, targ'ib qilish va ulardan foydalanish» 222-sonli qarorlari. www.lex.uz
4. Nomoddiy madaniy mulkni muxofaza qilishni Konvensiya2003 yil 17 oktabrda Birlashgan Millatlar tashkilotining Bosh Konferensiyasi tomonidan qabul qilingan
5. Boyakova O.A. Muzei etnograficheskogo profilya v kontekste obrazovaniya I kulturi Rossii : diss. Kandidata kulturologii : 24.00.03/ Botyakova Olga Anatolevna . – SPB., 2007. – 104 s.
6. Veshninskiy, Yu. G. Imidjelogiya rossiyskogo kulturnogo prostranstva kak opit vizualnoy antropologii (statiya napisana pri podderjke programmi po grantu RFNF № 06-04-00600a «Obraz Rossiya v natsionalnom samosoznani: istoricheskiy i sovremennyy kontekst»). G. Veshninskiy. – M.: RNII kulturnogo i prirodnoogo naslediya im. D. S. Lixacheva, 2008. – 57 s.
7. Sherbina, V. V. Sotsialnye texnologii: istoriya poyavleniya termina, transformatsiya soderjaniya, sovremennoe sostoyanie / V.V. sherbina // Sotsiologicheskie issledovaniya. – 2014. – №7. – S.113-124
8. Ashworth, G. J. From history to heritage—from heritage to identity. In search of concepts and models. Tourism, Culture and Identity in the New Europe / G.J.Ashworth and P.J.Larkham. – London: Routledge, 1994. – 1330 p.